

tropical American rice-growing areas is susceptible to the BSBR pathogen (see table). Previous reports limited the host range to the Gramineae; however, our results show that species from other families within the Monocotyledoneae may be hosts as well. The bacterium

was weakly pathogenic on a few dicots. Roots of most inoculated plants harbored the pathogen, usually in large amounts.

How rapid, or by what means plant-to-plant transmission may occur in the field is unclear and the extent to which

fields planted with clean seed may be recontaminated is unknown. Weeds may harbor the pathogen and the high recovery rate of the pathogen from roots suggests that plant debris in the soil also may serve as an inoculum source or survival site. *S*

Weeds as alternate hosts of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk in Cuba

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Many graminicolous weeds of ricefields have been reported to host *Thanatephorus cucumeris*. The resistance to *T. cucumeris* of some weeds was investigated under controlled and field conditions. Plants were inoculated under the leaf sheath with a 3-mm-diameter disk of PDA-grown culture of the fungus and covered with PVC bands to avoid desiccation.

Table 1. Reactions of weeds inoculated with *T. cucumeris* under controlled condition. RRS, Sancti Spiritus, Cuba.

Weed	Infestation (%)	Length of lesions (mm)
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	50	37.1
<i>Leptochloa fascicularis</i>	30	33.2
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i>	10	20.0
<i>E. colona</i>	10	20.0
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	10	3.5

Under controlled conditions, *Echinochloa crus-galli* and *Leptochloa fascicularis* were most susceptible and *Cynodon dactylon* most resistant (Table 1). In the field, *E. crus-galli* was very susceptible and *C. dactylon* and

Table 2. Reaction of weeds inoculated with *T. cucumeris* in the field. RRS, Sancti Spiritus, Cuba.

Weed	Infestation (%)	Length of lesions (mm)
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	100	80.3
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	100	40.3
<i>Leptochloa fascicularis</i>	100	25.0
<i>E. colona</i>	100	20.5
<i>Oryza latifolia</i>	100	20.0
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	100	10.4
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i>	70	10.1
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	50	9.2
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	40	18.0

Eleusine indica resistant (Table 2). Inoculations in the field were more effective than in controlled conditions.

Evaluation of decamethrin concentrations for tungro disease and vector control

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Different concentrations of decamethrin were evaluated under field conditions in a randomized block design. Taichung Native 1 (TN1) (susceptible) and Ratna (tolerant) were planted in 3 × 3-m plots. Decamethrin and cypermethrin were sprayed at 10-d intervals from 15 d after transplanting (DT) to 45 DT.

Carbofuran was broadcast at 15-d intervals from 15 DT to 45 DT. Three tungro-infected plants of cultivar Jaya were introduced into each plot just before the first spraying. The vector population was recorded at 30 and 42 DT and disease incidence at 49 DT. In TN1, disease incidence was low in

Efficacy of decamethrin concentrations on tungro disease incidence and vector density in TN1 and Ratna.^a CRRI, Orissa, India.

Insecticide	Dose (g ai/ha)	Disease incidence (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Leafhoppers ^b (no./20 hills)			
		TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna	TN1		Ratna	
						Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs
Decamethrin	200	3 a	2 a	3.3 a	4.7 a	3	0	1	0
Decamethrin	100	4 a	2 a	3.1 a	4.3 ab	5	2	1	0
Decamethrin	50	5 ab	4 b	2.6 b	4.0 bc	5	3	5	1
Decamethrin	25	6 b	5 bc	2.4 b	3.8 bcd	7	4	6	1
Decamethrin	12	10 c	5 bc	2.4 b	3.4 d	8	4	8	2
Decamethrin	6	81 e	5 bc	0.7 b	3.4 d	16	13	7	4
Cypermethrin	100	6 b	2 a	2.6 b	3.6 cd	3	2	2	1
Carbofuran	2 kg	19 d	12 d	1.4 c	3.5 cd	9	22	13	34
Control	—	100 f	44 e	0.2 e	2.4 e	51	152	43	104

^aSeparation of means in each column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bAv values of 30 and 42 DT.